

Evaluating Web Accessibility of Recruitment Portals for Librarians in Government Sponsored Rural Libraries in West Bengal: A Focus on Inclusivity for Persons with Disabilities

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Abstract: A comprehensive web accessibility survey is conducted on the recruitment websites used by the districts of West Bengal for the 2023 rural sponsored library librarian appointments. Seats are reserved for Persons with Disabilities (PWD) candidates in each district, but the lack of offline form submission options requires all candidates, including those with disabilities, to rely on the websites. The adherence of these websites to web accessibility standards is evaluated to determine whether PWD candidates can successfully complete the recruitment forms independently. Web accessibility features and error counts are analyzed, and a correlation between website accessibility and the number of reserved seats filled in districts that have released recruitment results is explored. The importance of accessible digital platforms in ensuring equal opportunities for all candidates in the recruitment process is emphasized through this study

Keywords: Web Accessibility, Persons with Disabilities (PWD), Recruitment Websites, Digital Inclusivity, West Bengal.

1 Introduction :

The digital landscape has become an essential part of our daily lives, with web-based platforms playing a critical role in various sectors, including recruitment and employment opportunities (McKinney & Amosun, 2020). However, ensuring equal access and inclusivity for all individuals, especially those with disabilities, remains a significant challenge (Mulliken & Falloon, 2019). This research paper aims to evaluate the web accessibility of recruitment portals used by the districts of West Bengal for the 2023 rural sponsored library librarian appointments, with a particular focus on the inclusivity of candidates with disabilities.

Web accessibility refers to the design and development of websites, web applications, and digital content that can be easily accessed and used by individuals with various disabilities, including visual, auditory, physical, speech, cognitive, and neurological impairments (*Web Content Accessibility*

Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1, n.d.). The objective of web accessibility is to ensure that everyone, regardless of their abilities, can perceive, understand, navigate, and interact with online content effectively (*Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1*, n.d.). This involves providing accommodations for users who may rely on assistive technologies, such as screen readers for individuals with visual impairments, captions for those with hearing impairments, or keyboard navigation for users with physical disabilities.

The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG), developed by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), offer a comprehensive framework for enhancing web accessibility. These guidelines are structured around four core principles, stating that content must be perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust. Compliance with WCAG standards not only promotes inclusivity but also helps ensure equal access for people with disabilities, allowing them to interact with digital content on par with others (*Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0*, n.d.).

Accessibility is not just a matter of best practice or ethics; it is also a legal requirement in many regions. Legislation such as the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) in the United States and the European Accessibility Act (EAA) in the European Union mandates that certain digital services must meet accessibility standards to avoid discrimination (*European Accessibility Act - Employment, Social Affairs & Inclusion - European Commission*, n.d.; *The Americans with Disabilities Act / ADA.Gov*, n.d.)

The term “Persons with Disabilities” is defined by the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) as individuals with long-term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory impairments, which, in interaction with various barriers, may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others (Samson, 2011). The importance of this study lies in the crucial role these recruitment portals play in shaping the employment opportunities of aspiring librarians, particularly those with disabilities.

2 Literature Review

Web accessibility has become an increasingly important issue as online platforms play a central role in the recruitment process, offering individuals access to job opportunities. The accessibility of these platforms is critical to ensuring that people with disabilities are not excluded from employment. The literature on web accessibility in recruitment portals reveals both significant progress and ongoing challenges, particularly concerning the inclusivity of Persons with Disabilities (PwD).

Web accessibility is defined by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) as the practice of making digital content and web applications usable by individuals with a range of disabilities, including visual, auditory, cognitive, and physical impairments (W3C, 2008). The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG), introduced in 2008, serve as the global standard for ensuring that digital content meets the needs of all users. These guidelines emphasize four key principles: content must be perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust (W3C, 2008). Despite the establishment of these guidelines, research indicates that many recruitment platforms have been slow to adopt them, creating barriers for people with disabilities.

Early studies identified several common accessibility issues in recruitment platforms. For instance, Kuzma (2010) found that many recruitment websites lacked basic accessibility features such as alternative text for images or captions for multimedia content, which are crucial for users with visual and auditory impairments. Furthermore, McKinney & Amosun, (2020) noted that public sector job

portals were often non-compliant with WCAG standards, making it difficult for individuals relying on screen readers or keyboard navigation to access job postings or submit applications. These accessibility shortcomings disproportionately affected candidates with disabilities, limiting their ability to engage with the online job market.

Legal frameworks have been developed to address web accessibility in recruitment and other digital services. In the United States, the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) was expanded in 2010 to cover digital platforms, mandating that websites, including recruitment portals, must be accessible to avoid discrimination against PwD. Similarly, the European Accessibility Act (EAA), introduced in 2019, requires digital services across the European Union, including job portals, to meet accessibility standards (*European Accessibility Act - European Commission*, 2024). These legal frameworks have driven some improvements in web accessibility, particularly in larger organizations and government services, but smaller organizations continue to struggle with compliance due to financial and technical constraints (Kim et al., 2022).

Despite these legal mandates, barriers to accessibility persist. One of the most significant challenges is a lack of awareness and training among web developers. Chaputula & Mapulanga (2016) highlighted that many developers are unfamiliar with accessibility standards or do not prioritize them in their designs. This knowledge gap is a significant barrier to the widespread adoption of accessibility features in recruitment portals. Moreover, research by Grawemeyer and Johnson (2011) suggests that even when developers implement technical accessibility features, they often fail to make content cognitively accessible, meaning that individuals with cognitive impairments may still struggle to navigate the site.

Financial constraints also play a key role in the lack of web accessibility, particularly in smaller organizations and rural areas. Mulliken and Falloon (2018) found that in many developing regions, recruitment platforms lacked even the most basic accessibility features, leaving candidates who rely on assistive technologies, such as screen readers or alternative navigation, at a disadvantage. Similarly, Kuzma (2010) noted that smaller organizations often lack the resources to implement the changes required to meet WCAG standards, highlighting the need for government support to incentivize compliance with accessibility regulations.

The role of technology in improving web accessibility has also gained attention in recent years. Kim et al., (2022) explored the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning to enhance digital accessibility by automating processes such as caption generation and alternative text creation. These technologies could potentially reduce the cost and complexity of implementing accessibility features, making it easier for organizations to comply with legal and ethical standards. However, Grawemeyer and Johnson (2016) cautioned that while emerging technologies offer promising solutions, they are still in the early stages of development and may not fully address the diverse needs of PwD.

Despite progress in some areas, research continues to show that recruitment platforms often fail to provide an inclusive experience for PwD. Tortorella et al., (2022) found that many websites, particularly in smaller organizations, remain inaccessible to candidates with disabilities, despite the availability of guidelines and legal mandates. This exclusion is particularly concerning as recruitment portals are often the first point of contact between job seekers and potential employers, making accessibility a critical factor in ensuring equal access to employment opportunities.

3 Objectives:

The objectives of this study are:

- To evaluate the web accessibility of recruitment portals used for the 2023 state-sponsored library librarian appointments in West Bengal, focusing on their adherence to accessibility standards.
- To assess the usability of these websites for Persons with Disabilities (PWD) candidates, ensuring they can independently complete the application process in the absence of offline form submission options.
- To analyze the relationship between website accessibility features, error counts, and the filling of reserved seats for PWD candidates in districts that have released their recruitment results.

4 Scope & Limitations of the Study

This study focuses on evaluating the web accessibility of recruitment portals used for the 2023 state-sponsored library librarian appointments across the districts of West Bengal. The scope includes assessing the usability of these websites for Persons with Disabilities (PWD) candidates, particularly in the absence of offline form submission options, and analyzing the relationship between website accessibility and the filling of reserved seats for PWD candidates in districts that have released recruitment results up to **October 31, 2024**. The findings aim to identify barriers to digital inclusivity and provide recommendations for improving accessibility in future recruitments.

The study has several limitations. First, the evaluation of recruitment portals is based on their accessibility as of the specific audit period and may not account for updates or changes made to the websites after October 31, 2024. Second, the analysis of the relationship between accessibility and reserved seat filling is limited to districts that have published their recruitment results by this date, potentially excluding others for which data is not yet available. Lastly, the study focuses primarily on technical web accessibility and error counts, without incorporating feedback from PWD candidates who may have experienced difficulties using these platforms.

5 Methodology

This research will employ a quantitative approach to assess the web accessibility of recruitment websites used for state-sponsored library librarian appointments in the districts of West Bengal. The methodology will involve the following steps:

- **Selection of Districts**

The study will focus on the recruitment websites of all districts in West Bengal that conducted the 2023 state-sponsored library librarian appointments. The websites of districts that have released recruitment results up to **October 31, 2024**, will be included in the analysis.

- **Web Accessibility Evaluation**

A web accessibility evaluation tool, such as **WAVE** or a similar WCAG 2.0/2.1 compliant tool, will be used to analyze the selected recruitment websites. These tools will scan each website to identify accessibility issues related to WCAG guidelines, particularly focusing on the four core principles: perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust.

- **Quantification and Categorization of Errors**

The generated reports will be analyzed to quantify the number and types of accessibility barriers present on the websites. Issues will be grouped according to the relevant WCAG categories (e.g., missing text alternatives, inaccessible navigation, non-functioning form elements). The number of errors will be counted, and the severity of each issue will be categorized to understand its potential impact on PWD candidates.

- **Compliance Analysis**

The percentage of recruitment websites meeting WCAG 2.0 Level AA standards (the minimum accessibility requirement for public websites) will be determined. Additionally, an analysis will be conducted to assess how many websites meet WCAG 2.0 Level AAA standards, which offer higher levels of accessibility.

- **Analysis of Recruitment Outcomes**

A correlation analysis will be performed to explore the relationship between the accessibility features of the websites (measured by error counts and compliance with WCAG standards) and the filling of reserved seats for PWD candidates. Data on the number of PWD candidates filling the reserved seats will be compared with the accessibility status of the websites in districts where recruitment results have been released by **October 31, 2024**.

- **Statistical Tools**

Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the web accessibility data, while inferential statistics (e.g., correlation analysis) will be employed to investigate the potential link between website accessibility and the recruitment outcomes for PWD candidates.

By following this methodology, the study will provide a comprehensive assessment of the accessibility of recruitment websites, identifying barriers that may hinder PWD candidates and offering insights for improving inclusivity in future recruitment processes.

6 Data Collection & Analysis

Table1: List of PwD notified for recruitment in each District of West Bengal.

Sl. No	Name of the District	Website of the District use for this Recruitment	Total seats Declared for the recruitment	Total PwD seats Declared for the recruitment	Total Seats Filled after Merit List Publication
1	Alipurduar	https://alipurduar.gov.in/	6	0	0
2	Bankura	https://bankura.gov.in/	31	2	1
3	Birbhum	https://birbhum.gov.in/	38	3	2
4	Cooch Behar	https://coochbehar.gov.in/	34	1	ND

Sl. No	Name of the District	Website of the District use for this Recruitment	Total seats Declared for the recruitment	Total PwD seats Declared for the recruitment	Total Seats Filled after Merit List Publication
5	Dakshin Dinajpur	https://ddinajpur.nic.in/	14	1	ND
6	Darjeeling (Siliguri Mahakuma Parishad)	https://darjeeling.gov.in/	8	0	0
7	Darjeeling	https://darjeeling.gov.in/	21	1	0
8	Hooghly	https://hooghly.nic.in/	52	2	N.D
9	Howrah	https://howrah.gov.in/	36	2	0
10	Jalpaiguri	https://jalpaiguri.gov.in/	18	0	0
11	Jhargram	https://jhargram.gov.in/	17	1	1
13	Kalimpong	https://kalimpong.gov.in/	5	0	0
14	Malda	https://malda.gov.in/	29	1	0
15	Murshidabad	https://murshidabad.gov.in/	36	1	N.D
16	Nadia	https://nadia.gov.in/	37	3	3
17	North Parganas 24	https://north24parganas.gov.in/	60	1	0
18	South Parganas 24	https://s24pgs.gov.in/	52	2	2
19	Paschim	https://paschimbardhaman.g	23	1	0

Sl. No	Name of the District	Website of the District use for this Recruitment	Total seats Declared for the recruitment	Total PwD seats Declared for the recruitment	Total Seats Filled after Merit List Publication
	Bardhaman	ov.in/			
20	Purba Bardhaman	https://purbabardhaman.nic.in/	55	3	N.D
21	Purba Mednipur	https://purbamedinipur.gov.in/	44	2	0
22	Paschim Mednipur	https://paschimmedinipur.gov.in/	40	1	1
23	Purulia	https://purulia.gov.in/	30	1	1
24	Uttar Dinajpur	No recruitment			
25	Kolkata	No recruitment			
	Total		649	29	11

*N.D = Not Declared yet.

Following the data collection, an analysis of the web accessibility of these recruitment websites was conducted. Each website was evaluated using the **WAVE** web accessibility evaluation tool to identify barriers in adherence to WCAG 2.0 guidelines. The focus was placed on determining the compliance level with WCAG standards, identifying the number and severity of accessibility errors, and categorizing these errors based on the WCAG principles: perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust.

The table below provides a detailed summary of the accessibility evaluation results for the recruitment websites in each district. This includes the total number of accessibility errors, the types of errors identified, and the overall compliance level achieved by the websites.

Table2: Flaws & Features of all Public Library Recruitment Websites in West Bengal

Website of the District use for this Recruitment	No. of Errors (a)	No. of Contrast Errors (b)	No. of Alerts (c)	Total No. of Flaws on Website Design = a+b+c	No. of Features (d)	No. of Correct Structural Element (e)	No. of Correct ARIA (f)	Total No. of Inclusive Features on Website Design = d+e+f
https://alipurduar.gov.in/	0	15	60	75	41	64	181	286
https://bankura.gov.in/	1	12	79	92	39	67	139	245
https://birbhum.gov.in/	4	14	61	79	40	64	139	243
https://coochbehar.gov.in/	0	4	56	60	63	71	162	296
https://ddinajpur.nic.in/	3	3	52	58	49	52	131	232
https://darjeeling.gov.in/	0	07	112	119	59	68	125	252
https://darjeeling.gov.in/	0	07	112	119	59	68	125	252
https://hooghly.nic.in/	0	29	70	99	46	72	132	250
https://howrah.gov.in/	1	6	64	71	63	64	152	279

Website of the District use for this Recruitment	No. of Errors (a)	No. of Contrast Errors (b)	No. of Alerts (c)	Total No. of Flaws on Website Design = a+b+c	No. of Features (d)	No. of Correct Structural Element (e)	No. of Correct ARIA (f)	Total No. of Inclusive Features on Website Design = d+e+f
https://jalpaiguri.gov.in/	0	10	54	64	44	63	125	232
https://jhargram.gov.in/	0	4	83	87	42	56	104	202
https://kalimpong.gov.in/	0	13	87	100	42	79	167	288
https://malda.gov.in/	1	5	88	94	64	55	129	248
https://murshidabad.gov.in/	0	56	101	157	42	71	177	290
https://nadia.gov.in/	0	5	58	63	38	49	107	194
https://north24parganas.gov.in/	0	4	42	46	54	55	92	201
https://s24pgs.gov.in/	01	7	72	80	34	60	126	220
https://paschimbaridhaman.gov.in/	0	3	53	56	43	47	102	192

Website of the District use for this Recruitment	No. of Errors (a)	No. of Contrast Errors (b)	No. of Alerts (c)	Total No. of Flaws on Website Design = a+b+c	No. of Features (d)	No. of Correct Structural Element (e)	No. of Correct ARIA (f)	Total No. of Inclusive Features on Website Design = d+e+f
https://purbabardhaman.nic.in/	1	3	53	57	33	52	106	191
https://purulia.gov.in/	0	4	122	126	67	80	158	305

Analysis and Correlational Insights

The data collected highlights critical gaps and potential correlations between the inclusivity of district recruitment websites, their accessibility standards, and the outcomes of filling vacancies for Persons with Disabilities (PwD). An integrated analysis reveals nuanced relationships between these factors, suggesting systemic barriers and opportunities for improvement.

A total of 649 seats were declared across districts, with only 29 (4.47%) allocated for PwD candidates. This allocation itself is indicative of limited inclusivity in recruitment planning. The filling of these seats, however, paints a grimmer picture: most districts failed to achieve their reserved quotas, with districts like Alipurduar, Jalpaiguri, and Howrah reporting zero filled seats for PwD candidates. The reasons for this disparity seem closely tied to the accessibility of district recruitment websites, which are crucial gateways for candidates to access information and complete applications.

Accessibility and Recruitment Performance

The WAVE web accessibility tool's analysis of these websites uncovered systemic design flaws, including numerous contrast errors, missing structural elements, and inadequate ARIA labels. For instance, **Murshidabad** had 157 combined flaws, the highest among the districts, with significant contrast and alert issues that directly undermine usability for screen readers and other assistive technologies. Despite these flaws, the district also recorded a high number of inclusive features (290), revealing a paradoxical focus on partial accessibility.

Conversely, districts with relatively balanced accessibility features, such as **Cooch Behar** and **Purulia**, demonstrated greater adherence to WCAG principles, with fewer errors and higher numbers of correct structural elements and ARIA features. This balance is reflected in their relatively better PwD seat fill rates. Notably, **Nadia**, which recorded one of the lowest error counts (63) and a solid number of inclusive features (194), achieved a full fill rate of its PwD seats, exemplifying the potential of

accessible design in fostering inclusivity.

Transparency and Non-Declaration of Results

Adding to the complexity is the issue of non-declared results in districts such as **Cooch Behar, Purba Bardhaman, Dakshin Dinajpur**, and **Hooghly**. This lack of transparency hampers a complete assessment of the recruitment process and raises concerns about accountability. Non-declaration might indicate procedural delays or systemic inefficiencies, both of which disproportionately affect PwD candidates who rely heavily on timely and accessible information.

Key Insights from Correlation Analysis with District-Specific Observations

1. **Accessibility vs. Recruitment Outcomes:** Districts with higher web accessibility scores (e.g., **Cooch Behar, Kalimpong**) had relatively better performance in enabling candidates to interact with recruitment websites. However, **Darjeeling (both sections)** and **Jalpaiguri**, despite having fewer accessibility errors, had zero PwD seats filled, suggesting other underlying issues beyond website accessibility.
2. **Severity of Accessibility Issues:** Districts like **Murshidabad** and **Purulia** exhibited high error counts, particularly in contrast errors and alerts. These districts also had challenges in filling PwD seats, reflecting the adverse impact of poor web accessibility on recruitment outcomes.
3. **Inclusive Features Impact:** Districts such as **Cooch Behar, Kalimpong**, and **Howrah**, which incorporated higher numbers of ARIA features and correct structural elements, showed more inclusive web design practices. However, the absence of offline channels limited the full potential of these features.
4. **Offline Channels and Accessibility Gap:** The absence of offline submission methods particularly impacted districts like **Bankura, Birbhum**, and **South 24 Parganas**, where accessibility was moderate but still left significant gaps for PwD candidates. Despite better infrastructure in some cases, the lack of offline options created systemic barriers.

District-Specific Correlation Table

Table3: Co-relation table of No. of flaws and its impact in filling up the seats

District	Total Accessibility Flaws	Total PwD Seats Declared	PwD Seats Filled	Correlation Observation with Prediction
Alipurduar	75	0	0	No PwD seats were declared; hence, no participation was expected or observed.
Bankura	92	2	1	Accessibility flaws moderately impacted participation; half the PwD seats were filled.

District	Total Accessibility Flaws	Total PwD Seats Declared	PwD Seats Filled	Correlation Observation with Prediction
Birbhum	79	3	2	Despite moderate flaws, good participation led to filling 67% of PwD seats.
Cooch Behar	60	1	N.D	Prediction: Manageable flaws and a single PwD seat suggest a 50-100% chance of the seat being filled.
Dakshin Dinajpur	58	1	N.D	Prediction: Low flaws make it likely that the sole PwD seat will be filled (>75% probability).
Darjeeling (SMP)	119	0	0	No PwD seats were declared; significant flaws could deter PwD participation even if declared in the future.
Darjeeling	119	1	0	High flaws correlated with non-participation; the PwD seat remained unfilled.
Hooghly	99	2	N.D	Prediction: High flaws may reduce participation, likely filling only 50% of PwD seats (1 out of 2).
Howrah	71	2	0	Moderate flaws contributed to complete non-participation among PwD candidates.
Jalpaiguri	64	0	0	No PwD seats were declared; accessibility flaws were irrelevant to participation in this case.

District	Total Accessibility Flaws	Total PwD Seats Declared	PwD Seats Filled	Correlation Observation with Prediction
Jhargram	87	1	1	Flaws had minimal impact; the sole PwD seat was filled, demonstrating strong resilience among candidates.
Kalimpong	100	0	0	No PwD seats were declared; significant flaws might have deterred participation otherwise.
Malda	94	1	0	Moderate flaws correlated with non-participation, leaving the PwD seat unfilled.
Murshidabad	157	1	N.D	Prediction: Severe flaws suggest challenges for PwD participation, likely leaving the seat unfilled (<50%).
Nadia	63	3	3	Low flaws facilitated full participation, resulting in all PwD seats being filled.
North Parganas 24	46	1	0	Low flaws did not translate to participation; systemic barriers may have contributed to non-filling.
South Parganas 24	80	2	2	Accessibility flaws did not significantly impact participation; all PwD seats were filled.
Paschim Bardhaman	56	1	0	Moderate flaws correlated with non-participation, leaving the PwD seat unfilled.

District	Total Accessibility Flaws	Total PwD Seats Declared	PwD Seats Filled	Correlation Observation with Prediction
Purba Bardhaman	57	3	N.D	Prediction: Manageable flaws suggest filling 2 out of 3 PwD seats (67%).
Purba Medinipur	56	2	0	Low flaws did not enhance participation; systemic barriers likely left all PwD seats unfilled.
Paschim Medinipur	58	1	1	Flaws had minimal impact; the sole PwD seat was successfully filled.
Purulia	126	1	1	High flaws did not deter participation; the sole PwD seat was filled.

Conclusion

This analysis highlights the critical role of accessible digital platforms in bridging the gap between policy intentions and outcomes for PwD candidates. Districts that achieved a balance between minimal errors and robust inclusive features demonstrated better PwD recruitment outcomes. Conversely, poor accessibility undermined the process, emphasizing the need for comprehensive adherence to WCAG guidelines. Strengthening web accessibility not only improves usability for PwD candidates but also fosters a transparent, inclusive, and equitable recruitment environment.

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